

Human Resource Accounting and Financial Performance of Listed Information Communication Technology Companies in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between the HRA and financial performance of listed ICT in Nigeria. HRA refers to the ways human resources are represented in monetary values in the financial reports to give a fair presentation of employee costs and value. Financial performance as the dependent variable was operationalized with the following variables: Human capital efficiency, organisational profitability, return on assets and return on equity. All the same, human resource accounting, which is the independent variable was measured with number of employees, gross staff cost and HRA-related costs (training, development, and welfare costs). A descriptive research design was adopted for the study and collection of data was done using secondary sources. The study is supported with Human capital theory. To achieve the objectives of the study, financial reports of ICT companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group as of 2022 were collected for the period of ten years (2013-2022). Purposive sampling technique was used to determine the sample size. Quantitative data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings revealed Human resources accounting variables jointly have a positive and significant influence on financial performance ($R = .926$, $R^2 = .857$, $DW = 1.53$, $F = 529.488$, $B = 2.489$, $t = 23.011$, $p(0.00) < 0.05$). The study recommends firms in ICT sector in Nigeria should invest more in human resources to enhance their productivity and competitiveness.

Keywords: Decision-making, Financial performance, Human resources accounting, Information communication technology,

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Introduction

Financial performance involves measuring a firm's activities and policies in monetary terms. The measurement should provide relevant information which is important for effective decision-making in an organisation. Most firms measure and disclose in their financial reports, costs incurred by the organisation with the corresponding benefits on physical assets only, while human resources-related costs- acquisition costs, training, and development costs, and welfare costs are poorly accounted for thereby, concealing the value or contribution of the human resources to the organisation. Eyes are always on the costs incurred on human resources like salaries, training and development, and welfare costs to keep them as low as possible. Reduction in costs and increase in profit may be achieved in the short run but, the impact in the long run on the motivation of the employees has been ignored.

Globally, with the conventional accounting practice, financial reports of organisations show all expenditures on human capital as charges against the revenue of the period. In financial reports of some organisations, only disclosure of wages and salaries serves as direct evidence of people in the organization. According to Kutieshat and Farmanesh (2022), Human resources are necessary substance of an organisation (Adeolu-Akande, & Oyedokun, 2022a).

Switzer (2020) sees an asset as a resource managed by the institution because of previous activities and from which subsequent economic benefits are anticipated to come to the entity². So, if an asset can generate benefits beyond the current financial year, then, expenses committed to training and developing employees ought to be acknowledged as an asset in the books of records. However, if Human resources are disclaimed as an asset in the financial statement of an organisation, it means the financial statement is not giving a true reflection of the situation of the organisation and could be misleading to users as a decision-making tool asserts Akinjare, Idowu, and Sule (2019).

Traditionally, any expense incurred on human capital is taken as an expense against the revenue of the period thereby reducing the profit of the period and, sub-optimising the financial report but the growing trends involve accounting for the cost incurred on the human resource as it yields benefits measurable in financial terms. This concept is human resource accounting, it is not a new concept in accounting but, contentious (Ilemona, & Oyedokun, 2020; Olalere, Oyegoke, Olorundare & Alao, 2023).

Bansal and Sharma (2019) defined Human resources accounting as a process of identifying, measuring, and communicating information about human resources to relevant users⁵. Ogunbiyi-Davies, Alao, Aremu, and Olalere (2023), opines that it emphasises using human resources as assets that generate income rather than as costs that reduce profits. It also involves calculating the financial contribution that each employee makes to the company⁶. Human resources accounting refers to the ways the human resources potentials are represented in monetary values in the financial reports (Idowu & Ajape, 2019; Oyedokun, 2022). Adewole, Ogunyemi and Ojo (2019) observed that human resources accounting is a developing research area in Nigeria (Mlanga, & Oyedokun, 2018).

The aim of this study is to investigate the human resource accounting and financial performance of listed Information Communication Technology Companies in Nigeria. Financial performance as the dependent variable is measured with the following variables: Human capital efficiency, organisational profitability, return on assets and return on equity while, Human resource accounting which is the independent variable will be measured with number of employees, gross staff cost and HRA-related costs (training, development, and welfare costs).

Business enterprises must make a decision regarding whether to classify human resource costs as capital or as expenses that are deducted from the revenue for a specified time period. The challenge stems from the requirement to improve the presentation of human resources in the organization's financial statement.

Amidst the current global challenges faced by business organizations, are issues like ineffective communication of employee value and unfair performance appraisal practices that diminish employee motivation, extensive research has been conducted both in Nigeria and internationally to explore the topic of human resource accounting and its influence on organizational performance in various contexts.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aims to investigate the relationship between human resource accounting and the financial performance of listed Information Communication Technology Companies in Nigeria.

The objective was to determine the joint influence of human resources accounting on financial performance in the listed ICT companies.

Research Hypotheses

H₀1: Human resources accounting has no joint significant effect on financial performance

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

The conceptual review attempts to describe the relevant concepts applicable to the study.

Financial Performance

The ability of organisations to create economic value has been described by various financial measures¹. (Tudose, Rusu & Avasilcai, 2022). Akinrinola (2019) refers to Performance as the actions and achievements of an organization over a specific time frame. It can be defined as the achievement of a predetermined task evaluated according to a predetermined standard of achieving correctness, comprehensiveness, cost-effectiveness, and efficiency². and can be ascertained from financial and non-financial perspectives. Financial performance considers the ability of a firm to achieve its financial objectives. According to Kusuma (2021), financial performance assesses items like the long-term viability, health status, criteria for making investment decisions, management accountability, and predicting the capability to meet expectations of future returns in the form of dividends, Interest, debt, taxes, salaries, and other obligations of an organization. A firm's financial performance can also be measured by using indices like return on assets, return on investment, profitability, return on equity, earnings per share (Adekoya & Adeniyi, 2020; Olayemi & Fakayode, 2021; Adeolu-Akande, M.A & Oyedokun, 2022b).

Non-financial performance indicators of a business evaluate long-term success and qualitative areas of a business (Refmasari & Supriyono, 2019; Adekoya and Adeniyi, 2020). The non-financial performance metrics encompass customer satisfaction, staff growth and development, and internal processes views (Switter, 2020; Taouab, 2019).

Human Capital Efficiency

Human capital is a crucial determinant of an organization's growth and development, and it significantly contributes to the effective execution of business strategies (Khan 2021; Tran & Vo, 2020). In the past, most organizations considered plants and equipment to be their primary asset. However, nowadays, human resources are recognized as the true asset of every organization (Khan, 2021). Ibarra, Garcia and Perhines (2020) describe Human capital as a vital component of intellectual capital and refers to Intellectual capital as the intangible assets that an organization holds, which enables it to achieve higher levels of innovation, productivity, and competitiveness but, are not disclosed in the financial reports.

The shift from traditional industrial backgrounds to knowledge-based economic systems for the achievement of business excellence has recently been a necessary issue of discussion (Rana & Hossain, 2023). A knowledge economy has been defined as an economy in which fundamental drivers of development and expansion are the generation, production, and utilization of knowledge. Historically, intangible assets were primarily characterized by their speculative nature and had a relatively minor impact. The valuation of a company was mostly determined based on its tangible assets. Currently, the significance of physical assets has decreased, while investments in information and other intangible assets have risen. Executives in businesses now prioritize non-physical assets to create a lasting competitive edge (Ali, Murtaza, Hedricakova, Jiang & Naeem, 2022).

Human capital refers to the intellectual and technical abilities possessed by employees inside an organization. Human capital is the most crucial kind of intellectual capital, and staff expenses are the most indicative measure of success (Alfiero, Brescia & Bert, 2021).

Tran and Vo (2020) explained the concept of Human Capital Efficiency Value Added Intellectual Coefficient (VAIC) designed by Ante Pulic for measuring the efficiency of intellectual capital within a company as the analytical tool developed to enable management, shareholders, and other relevant stakeholders to observe and evaluate the efficiency of the firm's total resources and each major resource component. The model measures value creation efficiency using accounting-based figures. One of the VAIC components is human capital efficiency. Human capital efficiency measures the value added by the human resources of an organization.

To measure Human Capital Efficiency, this study adopted the Pulic formula for measuring Human Capital Value Added.

$$\text{(HCE) Human Capital Efficiency} = \frac{\text{(VA) Value Added}}{\text{(HC) Human Capital.}}$$

(Rana and Hossain (2023); Alturiqi and Halioui (2020); Veselinoric, Krstic and Veselinoric (2021))

Organisational Profitability

Profitability is an estimate of the financial status of a company. It has been described as the adept of a firm to make profits from all its activities which are operating, investing, and financing activities. A firm must be able to generate revenue above direct and indirect costs incurred to generate revenue before it can make a profit. Also, maximizing shareholders' wealth means a firm can pay dividends consistently because of the appreciation of the worth of the firm's market share. (Koleosho, Adegbe & Ajayi- Owoeye, 2020).

A business with much profit will be able to retain adequate funds to support itself in economic breakdowns or financial stress. The higher the profits (with manageable risk) the higher the firm share resulting in greater prosperity for company owners. (Minanari & Rahayu (2020). Net profit is a measure of the basic profitability of a business. It is the revenue of the operation less the costs of the business operations. Revenue is the aggregate of the income a business makes through its sales. The proportion of that income that is left after deducting all the organization's expenses which it incurred in the process of making the revenue is the profit (Jayathilaka (2020).

Return on Assets

According to Khan (2021), Return on assets is one of the indicators used in measuring the performance of business organizations. It is the financial ratio that measures how effective an organization is in the proper utilization of its assets. Kusuma (2021) opined that Return on assets being a profit-related tool measures financial performance.

Therefore, the return on assets is represented by net profit after taxes divided by the total assets of the firm multiplied by 100 (Khan, 2021).

Return on Equity

Akbar (2021) asserts that Return on equity can be used to determine the performance of an organization in using an organisation's capital in providing returns to shareholders. The higher the ratio the better for the shareholders since it provides a greater rate of return to them.

Khan (2021) explains that a higher return on equity means an organization is efficiently using its shareholders' equity to generate income while a low return on equity means the organization makes little income when compared to its shareholders' equity.

The Return on Equity (ROE) is calculated by dividing Net Income by Total Equity. (Abu & Okpe, 2020). The return on equity can be expressed as the net profit after tax divided by the shareholder's equity (Khan, 2021)

Human Resources

Human resources are a crucial element of production and the most valuable asset a corporation may possess. (Oladejo & Ojokuku, 2019). The term "workforce" refers to the collective group of individuals employed by an organization. (Alekhya, 2020). Human resources refer to the people who make up the workforce of an organization (Onyewelu & Ironkwe, 2021).

Human Resource Accounting

To give a better understanding of the concept of human resources accounting, various researchers have defined it from various points of view which include the following:

Bansal and Sharma (2019) defined human resources accounting as a process of identifying, measuring, and communicating information about human resources to relevant users. This definition sees human resources accounting as an accounting system recognising human resources. while Abderraouf (2020) sees it as an information system that provides management with information on transformation occurring to the human resources of a business organisation for a particular period.

Gross Staff Cost

According to Adhikari (2020), Staff costs form a major part of an organization's functional costs. Mostly these costs include salary, wages, allowances, contribution to provident fund, training and development expenses, uniform allowance, medical allowance, insurance premium, pension and gratuity paid by the employer on behalf of an employee. It impacts the overall operational profitability of the business due to its running nature. The amount of staff costs incurred by organizations depends on the organizational policy, management's understanding of the welfare of its employees, and several other variables affecting the entity.

Development Costs

Development costs include costs incurred to enable employees to participate in development programmes to enrich their faculties. The programmes can be in the form of ordinary lectures, international conferences, and seminars. The participants can relate with other executives on a national and international level. The costs can include delegate fees, travel costs, loss of output during the development programme and so on which are to be accounted for as a human resource investment. (Akinjare, Idowu & Sule, 2019)

Welfare Costs

Employee welfare in modern times encompasses the various initiatives undertaken by employers to offer additional amenities and services to their employees, in addition to their regular compensation. Welfare facilities are crucial for the well-being of the company since they have a direct impact on the efficiency of the workforce³⁹. Research has shown that providing employee welfare benefits can increase employee engagement and promote staff motivation and performance in many firms. (Olalere, Oyegoke, Olorudare & Alao, 2023).

Review of Empirical Studies

Accounting for an organization's human resources falls within the purview of human resources accounting. It is important to take into account its connection to financial performance, just like with other assets.

In a study, using the Multiple Linear Regression test used OLS (Ordinary Least Square) model to analyze research data, Saputra and Manurung (2019) examined the influence of village governance duality and the implementation of accounting for human resources on the success of village fund management. The study also used the classical assumption test which includes the multicollinearity test, heteroscedasticity test, and normality test. The population in this study were villages that received village funds in the Bali Province which numbered 87 people and the research design in this study is a survey method using a questionnaire. According to the study, the implementation of accounting for human resources and synergy between village governments has a significant influence on the success of village fund management.

In another study, Alekhya (2020), looked at how the organization's top- and bottom-line growth was affected by human resource accounting. Five firms with a significant workforce that are implementing HR accounting systems were taken into consideration for the study. The study employed secondary data from 2013–14 to 2018–19. The bivariate correlation was the statistical method used in the investigation. The findings suggested that there is a connection between human resource accounting and both the top-line and bottom-line growth metrics. The application of the ordinary least square method yielded results that indicate a considerable influence of both the top-line and bottom-line growth indicators⁴⁷.

Additionally, personnel development and cost were used as a proxy for human resource accounting, and profit after tax (PAT), return on equity (ROE), earnings per share (EPS), and return on assets (ROA) were used as proxies for financial performance in a study. (Oginni, Olowookere & Ikotun, 2020) The study evaluated the human resources accounting and financial performance of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian stock exchange. Using the audited financial reports of ten (10) banks that were listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange between 2012 and 2016, descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and ordinary least square (OLS) regression were utilized to gather and analyze the data. The study found that HRA is statistically significant and contributes 69.7% to any favorable changes in PAT.

Thus, it follows that investing in human resources accounting could have a significant positive impact on deposit money banks' financial performance in Nigeria. The analysis concludes that the existing methods significantly undervalued businesses and suggests treating investments in human capital as assets that should be amortized over the course of their expected useful lives. Additionally, it suggests that pertinent regulatory organizations like the Stock Exchange Commission, Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria, and International Accounting Standard Board pass legislation requiring quoted companies to include Human Resources Accounting in their financial reports on a mandatory basis.

A study looked at the connection between certain Nigerian banks' human resource accounting disclosure and corporate determinants. The impact of listing age, business size, and profitability on human resource accounting disclosure was also investigated in this study. The annual reports and corporate websites of the chosen banks provided the data for the study for the years 2014 through 2018. In order to analyze the data and assess the research hypotheses, panel least square regression was used in the study. The results of the study showed a strong positive correlation between business size, profitability, and accounting disclosure related to human resources. Listing age did not, however, indicate a connection to accounting disclosure in human resources. Based on the results, it was proposed that in order to improve their social standing and lower the likelihood of agency expenses, Nigeria's listed banks be required to provide human resource accounting information. Additionally, by highlighting particular characteristics that gauge the factors influencing the human resource accounting disclosure of Nigerian listed banks, the study enhanced the already-existing models (Adejuwon, Olurankinse & Jinadu, 2020; Oyedokun, & Adeolu-Akande, 2022).

Abiola and Adisa (2020) conducted a study to investigate the impact of Human Resource Accounting (HRA) methods on managerial decision-making. Since the accounting, audit, and internal control staff members of 16 listed firms in the Nigerian financial services sector were thought to be the relevant departments for this study, a structured questionnaire on a 5-Point Likert Scale was carefully used to collect data for the study. A basic regression analysis model was used to analyze the surveys that were sent out and received back. According to the study, HRA significantly influences management decision-making within firms. As a result, it is advised that organizations utilize HRA more proactively to improve decision-making. To promote fair financial reporting and improve appropriate decision-making in business organizations, necessary and pertinent guidelines on the recognition of human resource costs in organizations' financial reports should also be provided.

Theoretical Framework

Human Capital Theory

Human capital was first introduced by the 18th-century Scottish Economist, Adam Smith as an improvement in human capability that is necessary for productivity (Lanre-Babalola, 2023).

The theory of human capital suggests the improvement of human productivity and efficiency through education and training; the proponents believed that education and training were investments that could add to productivity. Human capital refers to the educational attainment, knowledge, experience, and skills of an employee (Akinjare, Idowu & Sule, 2019)). It is the economic benefit of a worker's experience and skills or the productive

capabilities of people. It is believed that companies with high human capital funding in terms of training, salary and other benefits are likely to perform better than their contemporaries. (Khawaldeh, 2023).

According to Matashu (2022), Human capital theory assumes that education is important to improve the productivity of a population. It suggests that education increases the productivity and efficiency capacity of employees by increasing the level of cognitive stock of economically productive human capability that is, the natural abilities and investment in human being.

Conceptual Model

Source: Researchers Framework, 2024

Fig. 1 Conceptual Model

Methodology

A descriptive research design was used for this study to investigate the relationship between human resource accounting and the financial performance. The population of the study consists of all information communication technology companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group as of December 2022.

The sample size comprises the nine Information Communication Technology Companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group as of 2022. The collection of quantitative data was done through the use of the annual financial reports published by the nine Information Communication Technology Companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange for the period of ten years (2013-2022) on the website of Nigeria Exchange Group.

Model Specification and estimation

The ordinary least square regression analytical technique was used for data analysis to determine the relationship between a dependent variable and an independent variable. Results from testing these hypotheses will be statistically significant at a significance level of 0.05. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 was used to generate descriptive and inferential statistics respectively. The linear regression model developed for the purpose of the analysis is as follows to examine the relationship among variables of human resource accounting and financial performance

$$Y_1 = f(X_1) \quad (i)$$

$$Y_1 = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_1 \quad (ii)$$

$$FP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 HRA + e \quad (iii)$$

Where,

y= financial performance is the dependent variable, and

X = human resources accounting is the independent variable

FP = financial performance -organisational profitability (ORP), return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE).

HRA = Human Resource Accounting- gross staff cost (GSC), training, development and welfare costs (TDW).

$\alpha_0 \alpha_1$ = Parameter of the estimate

e = error term

$\alpha_0, \alpha_1 > 0$

Results and Discussions of Findings

The data used in this study for the analysis of human resource accounting and financial performance of listed Information Communication Technology Companies in Nigeria is presented in Appendix section.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
Human Capital Efficiency	90	-10.892	501.480	26.604	76.705
Number of Employee	90	0.000	4000.000	441.256	872.410
Organisational Profitability (net profit after tax)	90	7316716.000	318000000.000	23249474.856	66161669.516
Gross Staff Costs	90	0.000	394000000.000	29286322.077	78415897.064
Return on Assets	90	-999.833	37.902	-17.707	110.028
Training, Development Cost Welfare Costs	90	0.000	589000000.000	13262720.611	64890400.630
Return on Equity	90	-19.644	1.874	-0.345	2.587

Descriptive Statistics

	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Human Capital Efficiency	4.962	.254	26.502	.503
Number of Employee	2.831	.254	7.497	.503
Organisational Profitability (net profit after tax)	3.423	.254	11.707	.503
Gross Staff Costs	3.235	.254	10.408	.503
Return on Assets	-8.330	.254	73.610	.503
Training, Development Cost Welfare Costs	8.125	.254	71.528	.503
Return on Equity	-5.802	.254	38.100	.503

b

Descriptive Statistics of Variables

By measuring the financial performance of listed Information Communication Technology Companies in Nigeria, the descriptive analysis sheds light on the variables pertaining to human resource accounting. The financial reports of the nine information and communication technology companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group over a ten-year period (2013–2022) provided the data used in the analysis for this study.

The data presented in Table 1 indicates that the Organizational Profitability (net profit after tax) index has a mean of 23249474.856 with a standard deviation of 66161669; Gross Staff Costs index has a mean of 29286322.077 with a standard deviation of 78415897.064; the Return on Assets index has a mean of -17.707 with a standard deviation of 110.028; the Training, Development Cost & Welfare Costs index has a mean of 13262720.611 with a standard deviation of 64890400.630; and the Return on Equity index has a mean of -0.345 with a standard deviation of 2.587.

Human Capital Efficiency showed a positive skewness that was skewed to the right. The skewness is 4.962, the number of employees is 2.831, the skewness is 3.423 for organizational profitability (net profit after taxes), the skewness is 3.235 for gross staff costs, the skewness is 8.125 for training, development & welfare costs, and the skewness is -8.330 for return on assets and -5.802 for return on equity. These values indicate a leftward skewness.

In terms of kurtosis, a distribution that is larger than three and produces a sharper peak with a lower likelihood is referred to as a leptokurtic distribution. The kurtosis for human capital efficiency is (26.502), number of employees (7.497), organizational profitability (net profit after tax) (11.707), gross staff costs (10.408), return on assets (73.610), training, development, and welfare costs (71.528), and return on equity (38.100) all have leptokurtic kurtoses.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Human resources accounting has no joint significant effect on financial performance

Table 2: Summary of Regression Model of joint influence of human resource accounting on financial performance

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.926 ^a	0.857	0.856	16875849.59	1.53

a. Predictors: (Constant), Human Resource Accounting

b. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2024

Table 3 ANOVA Table of joint influence of human resource accounting on financial performance

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.508E+17	1	1.50795E+17	529.488	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.5062E+16	88	2.84794E+14		

Total	1.7586E+17	89
a. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance		
b. Predictors: (Constant), Human Resource Accounting		

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2024

The model summary of the regression model of human resources accounting indicates that there is no combined substantial impact on financial performance (Table 2).

The study of the model summary reveals that the multiple correlation coefficient R is .926, indicating a high positive correlation between the dependent variable (financial performance) and the predictors (human resources accounting).

Table 2 yields the following results: the R square (R^2) is .857, meaning that human resources accounting accounts for 85.7% of the variation in financial performance (the dependent variable). The error term and additional variables not included in the model account for the remaining 14.3%. Moreover, a very good fit of the model is indicated by the small difference between the R square (R^2) and Adjusted R square (Adjusted R^2) values, which is $.857 - .856 = 0.001$. The average distance between the data points and the fitted line of financial performance is indicated by the standard error of the estimate, which is often referred to as the standard error of the regression and is 16875849.59.

Since the observed value of the test statistic (1.53) is less than the tabulated lower bound, we reject the null hypothesis of non-auto correlated error in favor of the hypothesis of positive first-order autocorrelation. The last column displays Durbin-Watson, which is 1.53. From the table, the bounds are $dL = 1.635$ and $dU = 1.679$.

Table 3 shows how ANOVA table was used to determine whether the model is sufficiently significant. F – Value is 529.488 and was used to test the null hypothesis human resources accounting does not have any significant effect on financial performance. To do this, F needs to be compared with an F (1, 88) degree of freedom. The results in a p valve is given in the significance column, here p is quoted as .000 which is less than the conventional .05 level of significance.

Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis that human resources accounting does not have any significant effect on financial performance, and it can be concluded that there exists a significant variation in financial performance due to human resources accounting. Which means that the regression model is a good fit for the data.

Table 4: Coefficients of joint influence of human resource accounting on financial performance

Model	Coefficients ^a						
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	-264457.903	1886670.266		-.140	.889	-4013818.600	3484902.795

Human Resource Accounting	2.489	.108	.926	23.011	.000	2.274	2.704
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a. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4 summarized the regression model of joint influence of human resource accounting on financial performance. The regression model above begins with the coefficients that form the regression equation. The regression intercept (Constant) is -264457.903. When human resource accounting is zero, the anticipated value of financial performance is -264457.903.

By the regression slope, the B is 2.489 and is the amount by which we predict that human capital efficiency changes for an increase in human resource accounting of one unit. Both coefficients have associated standard errors of 1886670.266 and .108 respectively, that can be used to assess their significance, and in the case of the slope, to construct a standardized coefficient which is under the Beta column of .926. It represents the predicted change in the number of standard deviations of financial performance for an increase of one standard deviation in human resource accounting.

To test for the significance of the coefficients, we need to form test statistics which are reported under the t column. For the intercept, the t statistic is -.140 and the value can be compared with a t distribution to test the null hypothesis that the intercept $B = 0$, the p value is .889. So, we fail to reject the null hypothesis that the intercept is zero, and for the slope, the t statistic is 23.011 and the value can be compared with a t distribution to test the null hypothesis that $B = 0$, the p value is .000. So, we reject the null hypothesis that the slope coefficient on human resource accounting is zero.

Finally, the two columns show us the confidence intervals for the coefficients, and which show a lower bound of -4013818.600 and an upper bound of 3484902.795 for the estimate of the intercept. Similarly, at the 95 percent confidence interval bound for the slope (human resource accounting), B coefficient are .2.274 and 2.704, we reject the null hypothesis that the slope was 0.

Discussion of Findings

The following are the results of multiple regression analysis for the human resource accounting and financial performance of listed Information Communication Technology Companies in Nigeria.

The hypothesis was tested to determine the joint influence of human resource accounting on financial performance. The results indicate that the influence of human resource accounting does have a significant influence on financial performance. The rejection of the null hypothesis further emphasises the statistical significance of this influence, reinforcing the idea that the human resource accounting plays a crucial role in fostering positive and strong financial performance. These finding highlights that the variable contribute positively to the financial performance.

From the analyses and interpretation of hypotheses, Human resources accounting variables jointly have a positive and significant influence on financial performance ($R = .926$, $R^2 = .857$, $DW = 1.53$, $F = 529.488$, $B = 2.489$, $t = 23.011$, $p(0.00) < 0.05$).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings in this study, the study concludes that Human resources accounting variables jointly have a positive and significant influence on financial performance of listed Information Communication Technology Companies in Nigeria.

From this study therefore, recommended that Firms in Information Communication Technology sector in Nigeria should invest more in human resources to enhance their productivity and competitiveness.

This study contributes to the existing literature by examining the relationship between human resource accounting (HRA) and different measures of financial performance as moderated by Information Communication Technology (ICT) expenditure. The study provides a better understanding about human resource accounting and its benefits in ICT sector in Nigeria.

References

- Abderraouf G., (2020), *Measuring Human Resources Value Using Human Resources Accounting Methods and Models-Theoretical Study*, Elwhat for Research and Studies Review, 13 (2), 1416-1431
- Abiola J. O. & Adisa R. A.,(2020), *Influence of Human Resource Accounting Practices on Managerial Decision-making*, Archives of Business Review, 8 (5), 8-18
- Abu S. O. & Okpe J. U. (2020), *Dividend Policy and Profitability of Agro- Allied Companies in Nigeria*, European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research, 8 (8), 121-137
- Adejuwon A. M., Olurankinse F. & Jinadu O., (2020), *Corporate Determinants and Human Resource Accounting Disclosure of Listed Banks in Nigeria*, International Journal of Human Resource Studies, 10 (4), 303 -317
- Adekoya O. & Adeniji Y.A., (2020), *Impact of Social Costs on Financial Performance of Listed Firms in Nigeria*, European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research, 8 (11), 12-29
- Adeolu-Akande, M.A & Oyedokun, G.E. (2022a). An Appraisal of Effectiveness of Information Communication Technology in Office Management in the COVID-19 Era. International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI), vol. 11(03), 2022, pp. 28-44. Journal DOI- 10.35629/8028
- Adeolu-Akande, M.A & Oyedokun, G.E. (2022b). Office Management and Information Communication Technology (ICT) in the COVID-19 Era. International Journal Of Office Administration and Information Management (IJOAIM), 1(2), 88-102, <https://nioaim.org/>
- Adewole J.A., Ogunyemi J. K. & Ojo S.A., (2019), *Effect of Capitalising Human Resource Cost on Corporate Profitability in Ondo State, Nigeria*, International Journal of Shariah and Corporate Governance Research, 2 (1),14-33

- Adhikari N., (2020), *Training and Development Costs, Staff Costs and Operational Profitability in Nepalese Commercial Banks*, *Management Dynamics*, 23 (2), 109-118
- Akbar J. S., (2021), *The Effect of Return on Assets and Return on Equity on Price to Book Value on Banking Companies Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange*, *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research*, 5 (2), 9-20
- Akinjare Y.S., Idowu M. A & Sule .T. O. (2019), *The Impact of Human Resources Accounting (HRA) on the Performance of Nigerian Firms*, *JABU International Journal of Social and Management Sciences*, 7 (1), 252-265
- Akinrinola O.O., (2019), *Non-financial Performance Indicators and Operational Efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria*, *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 6 (12), 175 – 183
- Alekhyia P. & Lakshmi V., (2020), *Impact of Human Resource Accounting on Companies Profitability*, *Test Engineering and Management*, (83), 0193-4120, 16048-16055
- Alfiero S., Brescia V. & Bert F.,(2021), *Intellectual Capital-Based Performance Improvement: A Study in Healthcare Sector*, *BMC Health Services Research*, 21 (73), 1-15
- Ali, S, Murtaza. G., Hedvicakova M., Jiang J., & Naeem M, (2022), *Intellectual Capital and Financial Performance: A Comparative Study*, *Frontiers in Psychology*, 1-12
- Alturiqi A. & Halioui K, (2020), *The Impact of Intellectual Capital on Firms' Performance: Evidence From Saudi Arabia*, *Accounting and Finance Research*, 9 (4), 44-69
- Bansal A. & Sharma P., (2019), *An Empirical Evaluation on Performance of Organisation Through Human Resource Accounting: A Study on Selected Corporate Units of India*, *Indian Journal of Finance and Banking*, 3 (1), 1-12
- Ibarra M., Garcia M.R. & Perhines F.H. (2020), *Intellectual Capital: Organisational Performance and Competitive Advantage*, *European Journal of International Management*, 14 (6), 976-998
- Idowu T. & Ajape M., (2019), *Conceptual Analysis of Policy Challenge of Implementing Human Resource Accounting in Nigeria*, *Journal of Management and Innovation*, 5 (1), 1-18
- Ilemona, S.A, and Oyedokun, G. E. (2020). Human Resource Accounting and its Influence on Organisational Profitability. *SAU Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 5(2). 45-52. Published by College of Management and Social Sciences, Samuel Adegboyega University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria. sau.edu.ng/sjmss/index.php
- Jayathilaka A. K. K. R., (2020), *Operating Profit and Net Profit: Measurements of Profitability*, *Open Access Library Journal*, 7 (12), 1-11

- Khan S., (2021), *Impact of Human Resource Accounting on Organisation's Financial Performance in the Context of SMEs*, Growing Sciences, Accounting, 7, 621-628
- Koleosho A. O., Adegbie F. F. & Ajayi-Owoeye A. O., (2020), *Stock Market Returns and Shareholders' Wealth Sustainability of Companies Listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange*, Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting, 16 (2), 27-45
- Kusuma M., (2021), *Measurement of Return on Assets (ROA) on Comprehensive Income and Its Ability to Predict Investments Returns: An Empirical Evidence on Go Public Companies in Indonesia Before, and During the Covid-19 Pandemic*, JurnalIlmiahBidangIlmuEkonomi, 16 (1), 94-106
- Kutieshat R. & Farmanesh, P. (2022), *The Impact of New Human Resource Management Practices on Innovation Performance During, the COVID 19 Crisis: A New Perception on Enhancing the Educational Sector*, Sustainability, 14 (2872), 1-21
- Lanre-Babalola, F. O, Oginni, B. O, Ajibade, K. S, Olowu, A. E, Balogun, R.A, Tewogbade, S. O Ilori. O. A & Gbotosho, A. S, (2023), *Human Capital Development and Employee Performance: Evidence from Osun State Ministry of Human Resource and Capacity Building, Nigeria*, Journal of Behavioural Studies, 4 (2), 1-18
- Matashu, M., (2022), *Education, Human Capital Formation and Economic Growth in Sub-Saharan African Countries: A Conceptual Analysis*, Bulgarian Comparative Education Society, (20), 80-85
- Minanari M. & Rahayu A.,(2020), *The Effect of Profit Management, Good Corporate Governance Mechanism and Investment Decisions on Firm Value*, Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research, (120), 258-263
- Mlanga, S., & Oyedokun, G. E. (2018). Information Technology and Taxation in Eastern Nigeria: An Investigative Approach. Caleb International Journal of Development. Studies. 1, 1-92
- Oginni B.O., Olowookere J. K. & Ikotun A. O., (2020), *Human Resource Accounting and Financial Performance of Deposit Money Bank in Nigeria*, Nigerian Defence Academy Journal of Economics and Finance, 4 (1), 329- 341
- Ogunbiyi-Davies B. A, Alao M. E., Aremu P. O & Olalere M. D.,(2023), *Human Resources Accounting and Financial Performance of Some Food and Beverages in Nigeria*, Open Access Library Journal, 10 (8), 1-17
- Oladejo K.S. & Ojokuku R. M., (2019), *Human Resource Accounting Practices and Financial Performance of Nigerian Quoted Manufacturing Companies*, Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship, 11 (7), 147-167
- Olalere, M. D, Oyegoke K. S, Olorundare K. J. & Alao.M., (2023), *Human Resource Accounting and International Financial Reporting Standards (Pros and Cons)*, International Journal of Management Studies and Social Science Research, 5 (2), 111- 117

- Onyekwelu C.O. & Ironkwe U.I., (2021), *Human Resource Accounting and Corporate Financial Performance of Quoted Insurance Companies in Nigeria*, Research Journal of Management Practice, 7 (3), 20-39
- Oyedokun, G.E. & Adeolu-Akande, M.A. (2022). Impact of Information Communication Technology (ICT) on Quality Education in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions. *Himalayan Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 3(2), 49-58 Available at: www.himjournals.com/article/articleID=610
- Oyedokun, G.E. (2022). Environmental, Social and Human Resource Accounting: OGE Business Publisher, Lagos Nigeria ISBN 978-978-790-683-5
- Rana S. & Hossain S. Z., (2023), *Intellectual Capital, Firm Performance and Sustainable Growth: A Study on DSE-Listed Non-financial Companies in Bangladesh*, Sustainability, 15 (7206), 1-23
- Refmasari V. A. & Supriyono R. A., (2019), *The Effect of Non-Financial Performance on Financial Performance Moderated by Information Disclosure*, Journal of Economics, Business, and Accountancy Ventura, 22 (2), 248 – 263
- Saputra K. A. K & Manurung D.T, (2019), *The Role of Human Resource Accounting and the*
- Switter J., (2020), *FASB Conceptual Framework- Elements*, Accounting Standards Advisory Forum Meeting Agenda, 3, 1-17
- Synergy of Village Government in Village Fund Management*, Journal of Adv. Research in Dynamical & Control Systems, 11 (11), 303-309
- Taouab O. & Issar Z., (2019), *Firm Performance: Definition and Measurement Models*, European Scientific Journal, 15 (1), 93-106
- Tran N.P. & Vo. D.H., (2020), *Human Capital Efficiency and Firm Performance Across Sectors in Emerging Market*, Cogent Business and Management, 7 (1), 1-15
- Tudose, M. B. Rusu V. D. & Avasilcai S., (2022), *Financial Performance – Determinants and Interdependencies Between Measurement Indicators*, Business, Management and Economics Engineering, 20 (1), 119–138